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Multimorbidity clusters and their contribution to well-being among the oldest old: Results based on a nationally representative sample in Germany

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Data were taken from a large nationally representative sample of the oldest old in Germany.
- Four multimorbidity classes: relatively healthy; musculoskeletal; mental illness; high morbidity.
- Mental disorder cluster: low life satisfaction, lack of meaning & high loneliness.
- High morbidity cluster: high loneliness and lack of meaning.
- Efforts are required to address such vulnerable multimorbidity clusters.

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ABSTRACT

Aim: Our aim was to identify multimorbidity clusters and, in particular, to examine their contribution to well-being outcomes among the oldest old in Germany.

Methods: Data were taken from the large nationally representative D80+ study including community-dwelling and institutionalized individuals aged 80 years and over residing in Germany (n = 8,773). The mean age was 85.6 years (SD: 4.1). Based on 21 chronic conditions, latent class analysis was carried out to explore multimorbidity (≥ 2 chronic conditions) clusters. Widely used tools were applied to quantify well-being outcomes.

Results: Approximately nine out of ten people aged 80 and over living in Germany were multimorbid. Four multimorbidity clusters were identified: relatively healthy class (30.2%), musculoskeletal class (44.8%), mental illness class (8.6%), and high morbidity class (16.4%). Being part of the mental disorders cluster was consistently linked to reduced well-being (in terms of low life satisfaction, high loneliness and lower odds of meaning in life), followed by membership in the high morbidity cluster.

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Conclusions: Four multimorbidity clusters were detected among the oldest old in Germany. Particularly belonging to the mental disorders cluster is consistently associated with low well-being, followed by belonging to the high morbidity cluster. This stresses the need for efforts to target such vulnerable groups, pending future longitudinal research.

1. Introduction

In many high-income countries, a growing number of people are attaining older age and managing to survive diseases that were once considered terminal. Thus, it is expected that the population of older adults with multimorbidity will rise in the coming decades. Multimorbidity commonly refers to the presence of two or more chronic conditions within an individual (Nicholson et al., 2024). Multimorbidity is linked to, among other things, polypharmacy, lower quality of life, higher loneliness and a significant increase in healthcare expenses (Chang et al., 2023; Hajek et al., 2020; Nicholson et al., 2024; Olanrewaju et al., 2023). Previous research showed that the diseases commonly tend to manifest in specific clusters or patterns rather than randomly.

Previous research (Amirzada et al., 2023; Fan et al., 2022; Plasencia et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2022b) has identified several significant patterns of multimorbidity. There is some variability concerning which diseases are included or excluded in these patterns. Despite the variability in identified multimorbidity patterns across studies, some consistent multimorbidity clusters have been suggested – potentially due to shared underlying causes or common risk factors (Busija et al., 2019). A previous systematic review highlighted two predominant multimorbidity patterns frequently observed in the general population: one associated with mental health issues (such as mental disorders) and another related to cardio-metabolic disorders (including diseases such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, or hypertension) (Busija et al., 2019). In another systematic review, musculoskeletal disorder patterns were also often identified alongside these two patterns across numerous studies (Prados-Torres et al., 2014). Other studies also found mental/neurological multimorbidity clusters (Kirchberger et al., 2012), relatively healthy clusters (Bendayan et al., 2021; Marengoni et al., 2020; Ronaldson et al., 2021) and high morbidity clusters (Zhang et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2022a).

Previous reviews (Beridze et al., 2024; Busija et al., 2019; Rajoo et al., 2021) showed that existing studies did not exclusively focus on the oldest old (which is often defined as individuals 80 years of age or older). Moreover, studies focusing on the oldest old were often severely restricted in sample size and region restricting the ability to generalize the existing findings in this age bracket (Chen et al., 2023; Vetrano et al., 2022). Knowledge about the multimorbidity clusters in this specific age bracket is of particular importance because very old individuals can have specific multimorbidity clusters (with increased risk of complications) that differ from younger age groups. Moreover, as people age, there are more significant physiological changes which can affect disease progression and the effectiveness of treatments. A detailed understanding of multimorbidity clusters is required to design age-appropriate therapies, and better plan and organize health care to meet the unique needs of this population.

Furthermore, the few existing studies on multimorbidity clusters among the oldest old scarcely examined their contribution to well-being outcomes. For example, one similar study showed that both somatic and mental conditions were associated with poorer psychological well-being among younger and older people in Denmark (Tang et al., 2020). Another study showed that the psycho-cognitive diseases pattern was associated with low health-related quality of life, whereas cardiovascular-metabolic disease patterns were mainly not significantly associated with this outcome among community-dwelling older adults in China (Lu et al., 2024). However, these aforementioned studies did not explicitly focus on the oldest old. In light of the restricted knowledge, our aim was to explore multimorbidity clusters and, in particular,

to examine how different multimorbidity clusters potentially contribute to well-being (in terms of life satisfaction, loneliness and meaning in life). To this end, we used data from a nationally representative sample of individuals aged 80+ residing in Germany covering both community-dwelling individuals and individuals residing in institutionalized surroundings. We assume that a potential mental illness class in particular may be associated with unfavorable well-being outcomes (Hajek et al., 2023; Nie et al., 2023). We furthermore assume that a potential high morbidity class may be also associated with unfavorable well-being outcomes (Tang et al., 2020).

Regarding the rationale for this study, medical guidelines and healthcare systems tend to prioritize individual diseases which makes coordinating treatment for multimorbidity a significant challenge both therapeutically and economically. Investigating how diseases cluster and identifying shared pathological mechanisms can aid in creating new clinical guidelines and prevention programs. Moreover, tailored management strategies could be developed to improve patient care. Furthermore, this knowledge may inform policymakers and healthcare providers about the needs and care complexities of individuals in such clusters. This could enhance the treatment of multimorbid patients and reduce healthcare costs. In addition, knowledge of the relationship between multimorbidity clusters and well-being is crucially important to help the oldest old age successfully.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design and participants

We used data from the “Old Age in Germany (D80+)” study - a large, nationally representative sample of individuals aged 80 and older residing in Germany. The D80+ encompassed participants living both in the community and in institutional settings, such as nursing homes. The University of Cologne performed the D80+ study in partnership with the Cologne Center for Ethics, Rights, Economics, and Social Sciences of Health (ceres) and the German Center of Gerontology (DZA). Funding for the study was provided by the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (BMFSFJ). Data collection was carried out by Infas. This is a well-established institute specializing in market and social research.

In light of the pandemic, they opted for written questionnaires instead of the originally planned face-to-face interviews. Data collection occurred between November 2020 and April 2021. Further details regarding the D80+ study can be found elsewhere (Albrecht et al., 2022). Due to the focus on individuals with multimorbidity (i.e., two or more chronic conditions) and as recently recommended (Nichols et al., 2022), the final analytic sample comprised 8,773 participants (when loneliness served as outcome measure in the regression model). Notably, approximately 90 % of the individuals included in the D80+ study had two or more chronic conditions.

The ethical board of the medical faculty, University of Cologne, granted approval for the D80+ study (Protocol #: 19-1387_1). The questionnaire contained a brief introduction as well as a privacy statement. Respondents provided their consent by completing and submitting the questionnaire.

2.2. Multimorbidity clusters: chronic conditions

Overall, 21 chronic conditions were covered in the questionnaire: heart attack; heart failure (including cardiac insufficiency); high blood

pressure; stroke; mental or psychiatric illness (such as Alzheimer's disease, anxiety, depression); cancer; diabetes; respiratory or lung disease; back pain; stomach or intestinal disease; kidney disease; liver disease; blood disease (including anaemia); joint or bone disease (e.g. osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, arthritis); bladder problems; sleep disorder; eye disease or visual impairment (including macular degeneration, glaucoma or cataract); ear disease or hearing loss; neurological disease (e.g. Parkinson's disease, stroke with paralysis); (blood) vascular disease; thyroid disease. The selection of the chronic conditions was based on the multimorbidity index in old age (Diederichs et al., 2010; Diederichs, 2012). The resulting multimorbidity clusters served as key independent variable (with well-being factors as outcomes) in regression analysis (please see the Statistical Analysis section for more details).

2.3. Dependent variables

Life satisfaction was measured based on a widely used single-item tool ranging from 0 (completely dissatisfied) to 10 (completely satisfied), whereby only the endpoints were labelled. Former research has shown that such a tool is reliable and valid (Cheung & Lucas, 2014; Lucas & Donnellan, 2012). Loneliness was measured based on a commonly administered (Mund et al., 2022) single-item tool ranging from 1 (never/almost never) to 4 (always/almost always). The sensitivity of such measures and a high correlation with the UCLA has been shown (Nersesian et al., 2018). Moreover, favorable psychometric properties have been demonstrated (Mund et al., 2022). Similarly, meaning in life was assessed using a single-item asking about the presence of meaning in life, to which participants could respond: no, neither, yes. It has been dichotomized into: no/neither or yes.

2.4. Covariates

Based on previous research (Álvarez-Gálvez et al., 2023; Hajek et al., 2023), the following covariates were selected for regression analysis: Regarding sociodemographic factors, sex (male; female), age, family status categorized into five groups (married and living with spouse; married and living separately from spouse; divorced; widowed; single), type of living arrangement (private household; institutional setting), and education level classified according to the ISCED-11 framework (Bohlinger, 2012) (low; medium; high). Additionally, physical activity (no; yes) and size of the social network were incorporated as lifestyle factors.

Health-related covariates were incorporated as follows in regression analysis: Self-rated health was assessed using a single-item measure with four response options, ranging from 1 (very bad) to 4 (very good). Functional impairment was assessed using a modified version of Lawton et al.'s (1969) Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) tool, consisting of seven items. The final score was derived by averaging these items (yielding a range from 0 to 2, whereby higher scores indicate greater functional impairment).

2.5. Statistical analysis

As recommended (Nichols et al., 2022), latent class analysis (LCA) (Weller et al., 2020) was performed to identify the multimorbidity clusters. LCA is a multivariate statistical technique. LCA classifies individuals into latent classes that share similar characteristics. One can examine the likelihood of individuals belonging to each group and the factors that differentiate them. LCA was performed using the *gsem* command of Stata with the *lclass* option.

The number of latent classes were selected using different indices (Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), and the Bayesian Schwarz Information Criterion (BIC)) and considering the prevalence of chronic conditions. It is frequently used (Krauth et al., 2024; Olaya et al., 2017) when examining multimorbidity patterns and superior to conventional methods of cluster analysis (Karen Nylund-Gibson, 2018). Weights were

applied in all analyses to consider the sampling design and non-response (Angela Prussog-Wagner et al., 2022).

After that, the identified multimorbidity clusters were used as key independent variable in regression analysis. Linear or logistic regressions were estimated, depending on the well-being outcome used. Initially, unadjusted regressions were conducted. Thereafter, socio-demographic variables were adjusted in the regression models. Subsequent regression models included adjustments for lifestyle factors, and the final adjusted model included health-related factors.

Some of the variables had missing values (e.g., education had 3.5 % missing values; any missing values in the independent variables were present in 9.8 %). Thus, a full-information maximum likelihood approach (Von Hippel, 2016) was used (when linear regressions were estimated). Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$. Statistical analyses were performed using Stata 18.0 (Stata Corp., College Station, Texas).

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics and multimorbidity clusters

Table 1 shows sample characteristics (also stratified by multimorbidity clusters). Overall, 8,773 participants were included in the analytic sample, with an average age of 85.6 years (SD: 4.1 years, ranging from 80 to 100 years), 62.8 % of the participants were female, 39.7 % of the participants were married (living together with spouse) and 10.7 % of the participants lived in an institutionalized setting. Four multimorbidity clusters were identified via LCA and classified as relatively healthy class (30.2 %), musculoskeletal class (44.8 %), mental illness class (8.6 %), and high morbidity class (16.4 %). On average, multimorbid individuals had 5.1 chronic conditions (SD: 2.4), varying from 2 to 19 chronic conditions. Stratified by multimorbidity clusters, average number of chronic conditions was as follows: Relatively healthy class with an average number of 3.6 (SD: 1.5), musculoskeletal class with 4.4 (SD: 1.4), mental illness class with 7.6 (SD: 1.5), and high morbidity class with 8.7 (SD: 2.2). Further details regarding the different multimorbidity clusters are shown in Appendix 1. More details are shown in Table 1.

3.2. Multimorbidity clusters and well-being

Results of linear and logistic regressions with multimorbidity clusters as key independent variable and well-being measures as outcomes are shown in Table 2 (unless otherwise reported, the values stated refer to the fully-adjusted models). Compared to individuals in the most prevalent class (musculoskeletal class), individuals in the mental illness class had higher loneliness scores ($\beta = 0.20, p < .001$), lower life satisfaction scores ($\beta = -0.36, p < .001$), and lower odds of meaning in life (OR: .76, $p < .05$) in all model specifications. In nearly all model specification (only exception: final-adjusted model with life satisfaction as outcome), individuals in the high morbidity class had higher loneliness scores ($\beta = 0.07, p < .01$), lower life satisfaction scores (e.g., $\beta = -0.52, p < .001$; when adjusting for sociodemographic and lifestyle-related factors), and lower odds of meaning in life (OR: .78, $p < .05$) compared to individuals in the musculoskeletal class. There were occasional significant differences between individuals in the musculoskeletal class and individuals in the healthy class. However, no consistent picture emerged. Further details are shown in Table 2.

4. Discussion

Based on a large sample that is representative of people aged 80 years and older in Germany, our aim was to identify multimorbidity clusters and, in particular, to examine their contribution to well-being outcomes among the oldest old in Germany. We found that approximately nine out of ten people aged 80 and over living in Germany were multimorbid. Four multimorbidity clusters (relatively healthy class; musculoskeletal

Table 1
Sample characteristics of the weighted analytic sample (also stratified by multimorbidity cluster).

	Total sample N = 8,773 (100 %)	Relatively healthy class N = 2,655 (30.2 %)	Musculoskeletal class N = 3,928 (44.8 %)	Mental illness class N = 751 (8.6 %)	High morbidity class N = 1,438 (16.4 %)
Life satisfaction	7.1 (2.2)	7.3 (2.2)	7.3 (2.1)	6.0 (2.4)	6.6 (2.3)
Loneliness	1.7 (0.8)	1.6 (0.7)	1.7 (0.7)	2.1 (0.9)	1.9 (0.8)
Meaning in life					
Absence	1,903 (22.6 %)	544 (21.3 %)	685 (18.1 %)	256 (35.2 %)	417 (30.6 %)
Presence	6,535 (77.4 %)	2,016 (78.7 %)	3,100 (81.9 %)	472 (64.8 %)	947 (69.4 %)
Sex					
Male	3,262 (37.2 %)	1,337 (50.4 %)	1,252 (31.9 %)	172 (22.8 %)	500 (34.8 %)
Female	5,511 (62.8 %)	1,318 (49.6 %)	2,676 (68.1 %)	580 (77.2 %)	938 (65.2 %)
Age	85.6 (4.1)	85.4 (4.2)	85.4 (4.0)	86.5 (4.4)	86.0 (3.9)
Marital status					
Married, not living with spouse; single; divorced; widowed	5,215 (60.3 %)	1,418 (54.2 %)	2,330 (60.2 %)	541 (72.7 %)	927 (65.4 %)
Married, and living with spouse	3,434 (39.7 %)	1,199 (45.8 %)	1,541 (39.8 %)	203 (27.3 %)	490 (34.6 %)
Living arrangement					
Private household	7,833 (89.3 %)	2,343 (88.2 %)	3,629 (92.4 %)	588 (78.3 %)	1,273 (88.5 %)
Institutional setting	940 (10.7 %)	312 (11.8 %)	300 (7.6 %)	163 (21.7 %)	165 (11.5 %)
Educational level					
Low	1,975 (23.3 %)	505 (19.8 %)	870 (22.9 %)	203 (28.0 %)	396 (28.8 %)
Medium	4,397 (51.9 %)	1,283 (50.2 %)	2,048 (53.8 %)	385 (53.1 %)	680 (49.4 %)
High	2,094 (24.7 %)	768 (30.1 %)	889 (23.4 %)	137 (18.9 %)	299 (21.8 %)
Physical activity					
No	3,889 (44.3 %)	1,190 (44.8 %)	1,609 (41.0 %)	372 (49.6 %)	717 (49.9 %)
Yes	4,884 (55.7 %)	1,465 (55.2 %)	2,319 (59.0 %)	379 (50.4 %)	721 (50.1 %)
Size of the social network	7.6 (6.5)	7.6 (6.5)	7.6 (6.5)	7.2 (5.6)	7.8 (6.9)
Self-rated health	2.6 (0.7)	2.8 (0.6)	2.6 (0.6)	2.2 (0.6)	2.3 (0.7)
Functional impairment	0.6 (0.7)	0.6 (0.7)	0.5 (0.6)	1.0 (0.7)	0.9 (0.7)

Notes: Life satisfaction: from 0 to 10, higher values reflecting higher satisfaction; Loneliness: from 1 to 4, higher values reflecting higher loneliness levels; Self-rated health: from 1 to 4, higher values reflect more favorable self-rated health; Functional impairment: from 0 to 2, higher values reflect greater functional impairment

Table 2
Multimorbidity clusters and well-being outcomes. Results of linear and logistic regressions.

Independent variable	Loneliness			Life satisfaction				Meaning in life				
Class: - Relatively healthy class (Reference: musculoskeletal class)	-0.06*	-0.04+	-0.05*	-0.02	0.04	0.07	0.09	-0.06	0.84*	0.85+	0.87	0.80*
	(-0.10 - -0.01)	(-0.08 - 0.00)	(-0.09 - -0.01)	(-0.06 - 0.02)	(-0.09 - 0.17)	(-0.05 - 0.19)	(-0.03 - 0.21)	(-0.17 - 0.05)	(0.72 - 0.99)	(0.73 - 1.00)	(0.74 - 1.03)	(0.67 - 0.95)
- Mental illness class	0.45***	0.32***	0.31***	0.20***	-1.16***	-0.84***	-0.83***	-0.36***	0.42***	0.53***	0.52***	0.76*
	(0.37 - 0.53)	(0.25 - 0.40)	(0.23 - 0.39)	(0.13 - 0.28)	(-1.37 - -0.94)	(-1.05 - -0.64)	(-1.04 - -0.62)	(-0.56 - -0.16)	(0.34 - 0.52)	(0.42 - 0.68)	(0.41 - 0.67)	(0.59 - 0.98)
- High morbidity class	0.22***	0.18***	0.17***	0.07**	-0.64***	-0.55***	-0.52***	-0.07	0.51***	0.54***	0.55***	0.78*
	(0.16 - 0.28)	(0.12 - 0.23)	(0.11 - 0.22)	(0.02 - 0.13)	(-0.80 - -0.48)	(-0.70 - -0.40)	(-0.67 - -0.37)	(-0.22 - 0.08)	(0.43 - 0.60)	(0.45 - 0.65)	(0.46 - 0.65)	(0.64 - 0.95)
Sociodemographic covariates		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Lifestyle-related covariates			✓	✓			✓	✓			✓	✓
Health-related covariates				✓				✓				✓
Observations	9,186	9,186	8,974	8,773	9,147	9,147	8,932	8,739	9,040	8,607	8,413	8,195
(Pseudo)-R ²	0.04	0.18	0.18	0.23	0.03	0.11	0.14	0.25	0.02	0.08	0.10	0.15

Notes: Unstandardized beta-coefficients or odds ratios are shown (as appropriate); 95 % confidence intervals in parentheses; using the primary sampling unit, cluster-robust standard errors were calculated; *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, + $p < 0.10$; adjusted for sample cells; sociodemographic covariates: age, sex, marital status, educational level, living arrangement; lifestyle-related covariates: physical activity, social network size; health-related covariates: self-rated health, and functional impairment; sampling weights were applied. When loneliness and life satisfaction were used as outcomes, linear regressions were applied. When meaning in life was used as outcome, logistic regressions were applied.

class; mental illness class; high morbidity class) were identified among the oldest old. Particularly belonging to the mental disorders cluster is consistently associated with low well-being, followed by belonging to the high morbidity cluster. Our current study, which can be generalized to individuals aged 80 years and over residing in Germany, extends our understanding of multimorbidity classes exclusively among the oldest old. Previous research was mainly based on samples of general adult populations or older adult populations, without explicitly focusing on the oldest old. A unique contribution can be seen in showing how different multimorbidity classes are associated with important well-being outcomes.

Previous research identified a relatively healthy multimorbidity class (with few chronic conditions) in different countries (Ansari et al., 2023; Marzban et al., 2024; Otieno et al., 2023). Similarly, prior research also found a musculoskeletal class in middle-aged and older adults (Hu et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2016) which can relate to diseases such as osteoporosis and arthritis. A mental illness class was also identified in several former studies (Nishida et al., 2023; Roomaney et al., 2023) characterized, among other things, by a high prevalence of mental or psychiatric illness, back pain, and sleep disorder. A high morbidity class has also been described in previous research (Amirzadeh et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2023) often characterized by a high prevalence of a large number of

chronic diseases that are not limited to a specific body system.

Individuals belonging to the mental illness class in particular had unfavorable well-being scores (in terms of high loneliness, low life satisfaction and lower odds of meaning in life). These results seem very plausible to us, as such individuals must often deal with mental or psychiatric illness, insomnia and back pain (Chaudhary & Selvamani, 2021; Patel et al., 2013; Sagherian et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2021). Such factors can make life seem less worth living for those affected. Such illnesses can also make contact with friends and relatives more difficult and individuals may participate less in social life (Chaudhary & Selvamani, 2021). Thus, they may also be more likely to be avoided by others, as others may find the relationships very challenging (Janevic et al., 2012). Certain depressive symptoms such as anhedonia could also favor social withdrawal (Hajek et al., 2021). Sleep disorders and more severe pain could also be associated with an increasing withdrawal from society. These factors may explain why this class has a rather low level of overall well-being.

After the mental illness class, the importance of the high morbidity class is particularly noteworthy. In almost all model specifications, the high morbidity class was associated with unfavorable well-being. Potential explanations could be that - beyond functional abilities - certain processes of everyday life are more difficult for this group of people. Also, it may be the case that individuals belonging to this class are in particular need of help to manage their life (Hajek & König, 2016, 2022). In this respect, they could, for example, have many unidirectional relationships with caregivers (McKinlay et al., 2017). This could affect the quality of the relationship. In turn, the relationship quality may contribute to higher loneliness and lower satisfaction with life (Hawkey et al., 2008). The social and daily limitations associated with high morbidity may also lead to such individuals no longer seeing any meaning in life. It is also worth noting that the results of the relatively healthy class somewhat vary between the model specifications. For example, it was no longer significantly associated with loneliness when finally adjusting for health-related covariates. This may be explained by factors such as impairments in activities of daily living.

An important strength of this study lies in its usage of a large, nationally representative sample of individuals aged 80 years and over living in the community and individuals residing in institutionalized surroundings - especially the latter vulnerable group of 80+ year olds residing in nursing or old age homes are usually difficult to reach. Proxy-interviews were also conducted. Thus, the findings of our study are generalizable to individuals aged 80 years and over residing in Germany. Additionally, models were adjusted for several covariates and a FIML approach was used to address missing values. Furthermore, a wide array of prevalent chronic conditions were included. However, future studies could try to include even more chronic diseases (e.g., certain skin disorders or certain oral diseases such as periodontal disease). Furthermore, reliable and valid short tools were used to quantify well-being outcomes. Future research could explore this topic further by using multi-item tools. This study was restricted by its cross-sectional design. It is indeed possible that the observed associations between multimorbidity clusters and wellbeing outcomes are bi-directional. That is, for example, in addition to the high morbidity class leading to lower well-being outcomes it is possible that lower well-being outcomes also contributes to a higher level of multimorbidity, via as an example, participation in unfavorable lifestyle behaviors such as sedentary behavior. Future longitudinal studies are now needed to further elucidate on the direction of associations.

In conclusion, approximately nine out of ten people aged 80 and over living in Germany are multimorbid. Four multimorbidity clusters (relatively healthy class; musculoskeletal class; mental illness class; high morbidity class) were determined. Belonging to the mental illness cluster in particular is associated with low well-being, followed by belonging to the high morbidity cluster. This stresses the need for efforts to target such vulnerable multimorbidity clusters, pending future longitudinal research. Regarding future research, we thus recommend

longitudinal studies to explore the causal link between multimorbidity clusters and well-being.

Furthermore, interdisciplinary approaches involving social work, public health and mental health may also prove useful in maintaining the well-being of the oldest old. However, future research is needed in this area, especially among the oldest old (Di Rosa, 2022; Gadžo-Šašić & Ristić, 2020).

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André Hajek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Razak M. Gyasi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Karel Kostev:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Pinar Soysal:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Nicola Veronese:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Lee Smith:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Louis Jacob:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Hans Oh:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Supa Pengpid:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Karl Peltzer:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Hans-Helmut König:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

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References

- Albrecht, A., Kaspar, R., Simonson, J., Stuth, S., Hameister, N., Tesch-Römer, C., Wagner, M., & Zank, S. (2022). *Old Age in Germany (D80+): Representative Survey 2020. Scientific Use File Version 1.0*. Research Data Centre of the German Centre of Gerontology. <https://doi.org/10.5156/D80/2022/M.001>.
- Álvarez-Gálvez, J., Ortega-Martín, E., Carretero-Bravo, J., Pérez-Muñoz, C., Suárez-Lledó, V., & Ramos-Fiol, B. (2023). Social determinants of multimorbidity patterns: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Public Health*, *11*, Article 1081518.
- Amirzada, M., Buczak-Stec, E., König, H.-H., & Hajek, A. (2023). Multimorbidity patterns in the German general population aged 40 years and over. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, *114*, Article 105067.
- Angela Prussog-Wagner, S.S., L. Liebich, Prussog-Wagner, A., Schiel, S., & Liebich, L. (2022). *Methodenbericht: Deutschlandweite bevölkerungsrepräsentative Befragung hochaltriger Personen zu Lebensqualität und Wohlbefinden (D80+)*. infas.
- Ansari, S., Anand, A., & Hossain, B. (2023). Exploring multimorbidity clusters in relation to healthcare use and its impact on self-rated health among older people in India. *PLOS Global Public Health*, *3*(12), Article e0002330.
- Bendayan, R., Zhu, Y., Federman, A. D., & Dobson, R. J. B. (2021). Multimorbidity patterns and memory trajectories in older adults: Evidence from the English longitudinal study of aging. *The Journals of Gerontology. Series A, Biological Sciences and Medical Sciences*, *76*(5), 867–875. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/76/5/867>.
- Beridze, G., Abbadi, A., Ars, J., Remelli, F., Vetrano, D. L., Trevisan, C., Pérez, L.-M., López-Rodríguez, J. A., & Calderón-Larrañaga, A. (2024). Patterns of multimorbidity in primary care electronic health records: A systematic review. *Journal of Multimorbidity and Comorbidity*, *14*, 26335565231223350.
- Bohlinger, S. (2012). Internationale Standardklassifikation im Bildungswesen. *Berufsbildung in Wissenschaft und Praxis*, *4*, 16–19.
- Busija, L., Lim, K., Szoeko, C., Sanders, K. M., & McCabe, M. P. (2019). Do replicable profiles of multimorbidity exist? Systematic review and synthesis. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, *34*(11), 1025–1053.

- Chang, A. Y., Bryazka, D., & Dieleman, J. L. (2023). Estimating health spending associated with chronic multimorbidity in 2018: An observational study among adults in the United States. *PLoS Medicine*, 20(4), Article e1004205.
- Chaudhary, M., & Selvamani, Y. (2021). Association between back pain and subjective health, wellbeing and sleep problems among older adults in six middle-income countries: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of Public Health*, 1–10.
- Chen, H.-L., Yu, X.-H., Yin, Y.-H., Shan, E.-F., Xing, Y., Min, M., Ding, Y.-P., Fei, Y., & Li, X.-W. (2023). Multimorbidity patterns and the association with health status of the oldest-old in long-term care facilities in China: a two-step analysis. *BMC Geriatrics*, 23(1), 851.
- Cheung, F., & Lucas, R. E. (2014). Assessing the validity of single-item life satisfaction measures: Results from three large samples. *Quality of Life Research*, 23(10), 2809–2818.
- Di Rosa, R. T. (2022). Without social there is no health”: Social work perspectives in multidisciplinary healthcare. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 7, Article 1017077.
- Diederichs, C., Berger, K., & Bartels, D. B. (2010). The measurement of multiple chronic diseases—A systematic review on existing multimorbidity indices. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series A*, 66A(3), 301–311. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glq208>
- Diederichs, C. P. (2012). *Entwicklung eines Multimorbiditätsindex zur standardisierten Erfassung von chronischen Erkrankungen in der älteren Bevölkerung Hannover. Med. Hochsch., Diss., 2012.*
- Fan, J., Sun, Z., Yu, C., Guo, Y., Pei, P., Yang, L., Chen, Y., Du, H., Sun, D., & Pang, Y. (2022). Multimorbidity patterns and association with mortality in 0.5 million Chinese adults. *Chinese Medical Journal*, 135(06), 648–657.
- Gadzo-Sasić, S., & Ristić, I. (2020). Perspectives and challenges of interprofessional work in institutions for the elderly. *Human: Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(1).
- Hajek, A., Bretschneider, C., Mallon, T., Luehmann, D., Oey, A., Wiese, B., Weyerer, S., Werle, J., Fuchs, A., & Pentzek, M. (2021). Depressive symptoms and frailty among the oldest old: Evidence from a multicenter prospective study. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 22(3), 577–582. e572.
- Hajek, A., Gyasi, R. M., Kretzler, B., Riedel-Heller, S. G., & König, H. H. (2023). Determinants of psychosocial factors amongst the oldest old: Longitudinal evidence based on the representative “survey on quality of life and subjective well-being of the very old in North Rhine-Westphalia. *International journal of geriatric psychiatry*, 38(12), e6031.
- Hajek, A., & König, H.-H. (2016). Longitudinal predictors of functional impairment in older adults in Europe—evidence from the survey of health, ageing and retirement in Europe. *PLoS One*, 11(1), Article e0146967.
- Hajek, A., & König, H.-H. (2022). What factors are associated with functional impairment among the oldest old? *Frontiers in Medicine*, 9, Article 1092775.
- Hajek, A., Kretzler, B., & König, H.-H. (2020). Multimorbidity, loneliness, and social isolation. A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research And Public Health*, 17(22), 8688.
- Hajek, A., Volkmar, A., & König, H.-H. (2023). Prevalence and correlates of loneliness and social isolation in the oldest old: a systematic review, meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 1–23.
- Hawley, L. C., Hughes, M. E., Waite, L. J., Masi, C. M., Thisted, R. A., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2008). From social structural factors to perceptions of relationship quality and loneliness: the Chicago health, aging, and social relations study. *The Journals of Gerontology Series B: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 63(6), S375–S384.
- Hu, K., Keenan, K., Hale, J. M., Liu, Y., & Kulu, H. (2022). A longitudinal analysis of PM2.5 exposure and multimorbidity clusters and accumulation among adults aged 45–85 in China. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 2(6), Article e0000520.
- Jackson, C. A., Dobson, A. J., Tooth, L. R., & Mishra, G. D. (2016). Lifestyle and socioeconomic determinants of multimorbidity patterns among mid-aged women: a longitudinal study. *PLoS One*, 11(6), Article e0156804.
- Janevic, M. R., Rosland, A.-M., Wiitala, W., Connell, C. M., & Piette, J. D. (2012). Providing support to relatives and friends managing both chronic physical illness and depression: The views of a national sample of US adults. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 89(1), 191–198.
- Karen Nylund-Gibson, D. O. E. (2018). University of California, Santa Barbara; Andrew Young Choi, Department of Counseling, Clinical, and School Psychology, University of California. *Santa Barbara*. Ten frequently asked questions about latent class analysis.
- Kirchberger, I., Meisinger, C., Heier, M., Zimmermann, A. K., Thorand, B., Autenrieth, C. S., Peters, A., Ladwig, K. H., & Döring, A. (2012). Patterns of multimorbidity in the aged population. Results from the KORA-Age study. *PLoS One*, 7(1), e30556. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0030556>
- Krauth, S. J., Steell, L., Ahmed, S., McIntosh, E., Dibben, G. O., Hanlon, P., Lewsey, J., Nicholl, B. I., McAllister, D. A., & Smith, S. M. (2024). Association of latent class analysis-derived multimorbidity clusters with adverse health outcomes in patients with multiple long-term conditions: comparative results across three UK cohorts. *EClinical Medicine*, 74.
- Lawton, M., Brody, E., & Médecin, U. (1969). Instrumental activities of daily living (IADL). *The Gerontologist*, 9, 179–186.
- Lu, H., Dong, X.-X., Li, D.-L., Nie, X.-Y., Wang, P., & Pan, C.-W. (2024). Multimorbidity patterns and health-related quality of life among community-dwelling older adults: evidence from a rural town in Suzhou, China. *Quality of Life Research*, 33(5), 1335–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-024-03608-0>
- Lucas, R. E., & Donnellan, M. B. (2012). Estimating the reliability of single-item life satisfaction measures: Results from four national panel studies. *Social Indicators Research*, 105(3), 323–331.
- Marengoni, A., Roso-Llorach, A., Vetrano, D. L., Fernández-Bertolín, S., Guisado-Clavero, M., Violán, C., & Calderón-Larrañaga, A. (2020). Patterns of multimorbidity in a population-based cohort of older people: Sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical, and functional differences. *The Journals of Gerontology. Series A, Biological Sciences and Medical Sciences*, 75(4), 798–805. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glz137>
- Marzban, M., Jamshidi, A., Khorrami, Z., Hall, M., Batty, J. A., Farhadi, A., Mahmudpour, M., Gholizade, M., Nabipour, I., & Larjani, B. (2024). Determinants of multimorbidity in older adults in Iran: A cross-sectional study using latent class analysis on the Bushehr Elderly Health (BEH) program. *BMC Geriatrics*, 24(1), 247.
- McKinlay, E., McDonald, J., Darlow, B., & Perry, M. (2017). Social networks of patients with multimorbidity: a qualitative study of patients’ and supporters’ views. *Journal of Primary Health Care*, 9(2), 153–161.
- Mund, M., Maes, M., Drewke, P. M., Gutzeit, A., Jaki, I., & Qualter, P. (2022). Would the real loneliness please stand up? The validity of loneliness scores and the reliability of single-item scores. *Assessment*, 10731911221077227.
- Nerkesian, P. V., Han, H.-R., Yenokyan, G., Blumenthal, R. S., Nolan, M. T., Hladek, M. D., & Szanton, S. L. (2018). Loneliness in middle age and biomarkers of systemic inflammation: Findings from midlife in the United States. *Social Science & Medicine*, 209, 174–181.
- Nichols, L., Taverner, T., Crowe, F., Richardson, S., Yau, C., Kiddle, S., Kirk, P., Barrett, J., Nirantharakumar, K., & Griffin, S. (2022). In simulated data and health records, latent class analysis was the optimum multimorbidity clustering algorithm. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 152, 164–175.
- Nicholson, K., Liu, W., Fitzpatrick, D., Hardacre, K. A., Roberts, S., Salerno, J., Stranges, S., Fortin, M., & Mangin, D. (2024). Prevalence of multimorbidity and polypharmacy among adults and older adults: A systematic review. *The Lancet Healthy Longevity*.
- Nie, S., Lim, J., Xu, X., Zheng, L., & Gan, Y. (2023). Meaning in life and mental health issues in older adults: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Mental Health Promotion*, 25(9).
- Nishida, Y., Anzai, T., Takahashi, K., Kozuma, T., Kanda, E., Yamauchi, K., & Katsukawa, F. (2023). Multimorbidity patterns in the working age population with the top 10% medical cost from exhaustive insurance claims data of Japan Health Insurance Association. *PLoS one*, 18(9), Article e0291554.
- Olanrewaju, O., Trott, M., Smith, L., López Sánchez, G. F., Carmichael, C., Oh, H., Schuff, F., Jacob, L., Veronese, N., & Soysal, P. (2023). Chronic physical conditions, physical multimorbidity, and quality of life among adults aged ≥ 50 years from six low-and middle-income countries. *Quality of Life Research*, 32(4), 1031–1041.
- Olaya, B., Moneta, M. V., Caballero, F. F., Tyrovolas, S., Bayes, I., Ayuso-Mateos, J. L., & Haro, J. M. (2017). Latent class analysis of multimorbidity patterns and associated outcomes in Spanish older adults: a prospective cohort study. *BMC Geriatrics*, 17, 1–10.
- Otieno, P., Asiki, G., Wekesah, F., Wilunda, C., Sanya, R. E., Wami, W., & Agyemang, C. (2023). Multimorbidity of cardiometabolic diseases: a cross-sectional study of patterns, clusters and associated risk factors in sub-Saharan Africa. *BMJ Open*, 13(2), Article e064275.
- Patel, K. V., Guralnik, J. M., Dansie, E. J., & Turk, D. C. (2013). Prevalence and impact of pain among older adults in the United States: findings from the 2011 National Health and Aging Trends Study. *Pain®*, 154(12), 2649–2657.
- Plasencia, G., Gray, S. C., Hall, I. J., & Smith, J. L. (2024). Multimorbidity clusters in adults 50 years or older with and without a history of cancer: National Health Interview Survey, 2018. *BMC Geriatrics*, 24(1), 50.
- Prados-Torres, A., Calderón-Larrañaga, A., Hanco-Saavedra, J., Poblador-Plou, B., & van den Akker, M. (2014). Multimorbidity patterns: a systematic review. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 67(3), 254–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2013.09.021>
- Rajoo, S. S., Wee, Z. J., Lee, P. S. S., Wong, F. Y., & Lee, E. S. (2021). A systematic review of the patterns of associative multimorbidity in Asia. *BioMed Research International*, 2021(1), Article 6621785.
- Ronaldson, A., Arias de la Torre, J., Prina, M., Armstrong, D., Das-Munshi, J., Hatch, S., Stewart, R., Hotopf, M., & Dregan, A. (2021). Associations between physical multimorbidity patterns and common mental health disorders in middle-aged adults: A prospective analysis using data from the UK Biobank. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe*, 8, Article 100149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2021.100149>
- Roomaney, R. A., Van Wyk, B., Cois, A., & Pillay van-Wyk, V. (2023). Multimorbidity patterns in South Africa: A latent class analysis. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, Article 1082587.
- Sagherian, K., Steege, L. M., Cobb, S. J., & Cho, H. (2023). Insomnia, fatigue and psychosocial well-being during COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional survey of hospital nursing staff in the United States. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 32(15-16), 5382–5395.
- Tang, L. H., Thygesen, L. C., Willadsen, T. G., Jepsen, R., la Cour, K., Frølich, A., Møller, A., Jørgensen, L. B., & Skou, S. T. (2020). The association between clusters of chronic conditions and psychological well-being in younger and older people—a cross-sectional, population-based study from the Lolland-Falster health study, Denmark. *Journal of Comorbidity*, 10, 2235042X20981185.
- Vetrano, D. L., Damiano, C., Tazzeo, C., Zucchelli, A., Marengoni, A., Luo, H., Zazzara, M. B., van Hout, H., & Onder, G. (2022). Multimorbidity patterns and 5-year mortality in institutionalized older adults. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 23(8), 1389–1395. e1384.
- Von Hippel, P. T. (2016). New confidence intervals and bias comparisons show that maximum likelihood can beat multiple imputation in small samples. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 23(3), 422–437.
- Weller, B. E., Bowen, N. K., & Faubert, S. J. (2020). Latent class analysis: A guide to best practice. *Journal of Black Psychology*, 46(4), 287–311. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095798420930932>
- Zhang, Q., Han, X., Zhao, X., & Wang, Y. (2022). Multimorbidity patterns and associated factors in older Chinese: results from the China health and retirement longitudinal study. *BMC geriatrics*, 22(1), 470.

- Zhao, X., Zhang, Q., Ma, C., Liu, H., & Chen, Y. (2023). Association between multimorbidity patterns and healthcare costs among middle-aged and older adults in China. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, *109*, Article 104959.
- Zhou, F., Guo, Y., Wang, Z., Liu, S., & Xu, H. (2021). Assessing the causal associations of insomnia with depressive symptoms and subjective well-being: a bidirectional Mendelian randomization study. *Sleep Medicine*, *87*, 85–91.

- Zhou, J., Wei, M. Y., Zhang, J., Liu, H., & Wu, C. (2022a). Association of multimorbidity patterns with incident disability and recovery of independence among middle-aged and older adults. *Age and Ageing*, *51*(8). <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afac177>
- Zhou, J., Wei, M. Y., Zhang, J., Liu, H., & Wu, C. (2022b). Association of multimorbidity patterns with incident disability and recovery of independence among middle-aged and older adults. *Age and Ageing*, *51*(8), afac177.